

NEXOS: A Decision-Support Tool for the Next Release Problem in Software Engineering

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Abstract

The selection of requirements to compose a release has become an increasingly complex and strategic task for technology teams. This complexity stems from the growing demand for rapid delivery of new features, combined with the need to maintain quality and ensure the sustainability of software lifecycle management. In this context, it is essential to address the challenges faced by teams through solutions that automate scope definition, reduce planning time, and minimize errors caused by misaligned prioritization. Although some studies have addressed the Next Release Problem using various algorithms, few have focused on developing practical applications that can also serve as tools for Application Lifecycle Management (ALM). This work presents NEXOS (Next Release Optimization System), a system designed to support release planning through the application of greedy algorithms. The proposed tool aims to assist in the selection of requirements based on user-defined criteria, taking into account budget constraints, client importance, requirement relevance, and dependencies between requirements. NEXOS was tested across different testing levels, including acceptance testing with 7 participants. Among other findings, the results of the System Usability Scale (SUS) indicate that users are willing to recommend the system, according to the semantics of the SUS results. As its main contribution, NEXOS seeks to support project managers in decision-making, enabling deliveries that are better aligned with business priorities and ensuring more efficient use of available resources¹.

Keywords

Next release problem; Greedy Algorithms; Optimization

1 Introduction

The efficient construction of software releases has become a strategic task in modern software engineering, driven by the constant demand for new functionalities and the need to ensure quality and sustainability throughout the system's lifecycle[14]. One of the main challenges faced by development teams is the careful selection of requirements that will compose each release, considering constraints such as time, budget, business priorities, and interdependencies among features.

Within this context, the Next Release Problem (NRP) emerges as a key concept, introduced by[1] during a workshop on the application of metaheuristic techniques to software engineering. The NRP aims to determine the optimal subset of requirements to be included in the next software release, balancing multiple constraints and goals. This decision becomes even more complex due to the dependencies

between requirements—approximately 80% are interrelated—which significantly affects scope definition and project success[4].

Poorly made decisions in this process can seriously compromise project outcomes, leading to stakeholder dissatisfaction, budget overruns, or resource waste[12]. To mitigate such risks, optimization algorithms have been explored as decision-support tools. Among them, greedy algorithms stand out due to their simplicity and efficiency in scenarios where optimal solutions can be approached incrementally[5].

This work presents NEXOS (Next Release Problem Optimization System), a system designed to support scope definition through the application of greedy algorithms. The tool aims to automate the selection of requirements based on variables such as available budget, customer importance, requirement priority, and interdependencies defined by the user. The proposal seeks not only to optimize planning time and reduce prioritization errors but also to function as a decision-support tool for project managers, promoting releases that are aligned with business strategies.

2 Related Work

This section presents the studies that inspired the development of this final project, as well as the main functionalities they offer. The reviewed works include a research initiative conducted by a Brazilian university, highlighting advancements in the academic environment, and a collaborative application.

2.1 Optimization Algorithms for Solving the Next Release Problem

This work[15] explores a variety of optimization algorithms to address the Next Release Problem (NRP), including exact methods such as Exhaustive Search, Dynamic Programming, and Branch and Bound, as well as heuristics and metaheuristics such as Greedy Algorithm, Genetic Algorithm, and Simulated Annealing. These algorithms were evaluated using both randomly generated instances and a real-world case study from a company based in Recife, Brazil. The modeling was adapted to reflect the company's specific context. The objective of this study is to contribute to the understanding and effective resolution of the NRP, offering a comprehensive comparison of exact, heuristic, and metaheuristic approaches.

The results indicate that exact algorithms perform well on small instances but become impractical as the number of requirements increases, due to high computational costs. In contrast, heuristics and metaheuristics—despite not guaranteeing an optimal solution—achieve satisfactory results with greater efficiency in larger instances. Among them, the Greedy Algorithm delivered the best outcomes, although its execution time also increased significantly and it lacked improvement strategies.

¹<https://youtu.be/wDTW8Cy-POc?si=cQGSqo7dEJ6kSM4v>

2.2 Next Release Tool

The Next Release Tool is a demonstration tool designed to allow users to input requirements and compute the optimal solution to the Next Release Problem. The requirement modeling language used is goal-oriented, with its main constructs and relationships detailed in the previous section. The tool is available for Windows, macOS, and Linux platforms and can be downloaded on the website². An overview of the Next Release Tool interface is shown in Figure 1, where the main components of the environment can be seen.

Figure 1: Next Release Tool

The tool allows users to import existing models or build new ones from scratch. Requirements and their interrelationships are defined through a graphical user interface. A palette provides visual elements representing concepts and connectors for different types of relationships and refinements. Users can drag and drop these elements into the workspace to construct their models. Figure 2 illustrates how the tool is used in practice to define and manipulate requirement models.

Figure 2: Next Release Tool usage

2.3 Comparison with NEXOS

While previous works investigate optimization algorithms to solve the NRP and present the Next Release Tool as a solution, this study aims to go further by providing a more usability-oriented alternative tailored for project managers. The system proposed in this work seeks to overcome and innovate the issues by offering a web-accessible interface and aims to support software development teams in selecting and prioritizing requirements to define software releases more efficiently. Targeting project managers and requirements analysts, NEXOS applies greedy algorithms to address the Next Release Problem, helping optimize the scope based on configurable variables such as cost, priority, and stakeholder value.

²<https://www.nextrelease.eu>

FEATURES	NEXOS	Thesis	NRT
Developed greedy algorithms to solve the problem	X	X	
Developed an application	X		
Created a web graphical interface	X		X
Considers the total release cost to define scope	X	X	X
Used current programming tools for development	X		X
Application saves user-created releases for later access	X		X

Table 1: Comparison of features

3 Mathematical Formulation

NEXOS proposes to address the NRP issue by searching for the optimal set of requirements that best meets customer demands while adhering to the financial constraints imposed by the budget for the next release.

Accordingly, the mathematical model expressed by Equations 1 – 5 presents the objective function used and the constraints that must be respected in order to find an optimal solution.

$$\text{maximize } \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m X_i \cdot P_{ij} \cdot W_j \quad (1)$$

$$\text{subject to } \sum_{i=1}^n C_i \cdot X_i \leq b \quad (2)$$

$$X_k \leq X_l, \quad \forall (k, l) \in D \quad (3)$$

$$X_i \in \{0, 1\}, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n \quad (4)$$

$$Y_j \in \{0, 1\}, \quad 1 \leq j \leq m \quad (5)$$

Considering n as the number of software requirements to be handled by the development team, the decision variable X_i indicates whether a given requirement is included or excluded in the next release (Equation 4). Each requirement n has an associated implementation cost, represented by the variable C_i , where $i = \{1, \dots, n\}$.

Each client m is associated with the decision variable Y_j , indicating whether the client will be served in the next release (Equation 5), as well as with the variable W_j , which measures the client's importance to the company developing the software.

The issue of requirement interdependencies is addressed through constraint (Equation 8), ensuring that if a requirement X_k depends on another requirement X_l , then X_l must be implemented whenever X_k is selected.

$$\text{maximize } \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m X_i \cdot P_{ij} \cdot W_j \quad (6)$$

The objective function (Equation 6) maximizes the importance W_j of the clients weighted by the importance P_{ij} of the requirements for each client.

Constraint (Equation 7) relates to the implementation cost limitation, where C_i is the implementation cost of requirement X_i , and b is the company's budget limit.

$$\sum_{i=1}^n C_i \cdot X_i \leq b \quad (7)$$

Constraint (Equation 8) ensures that if a requirement X_k depends on another X_l , then X_l must be included whenever X_k is selected.

$$X_k \leq X_l, \quad \forall (k, l) \in D \quad (8)$$

In this context, the greedy algorithm stands out, characterized by always choosing the option that seems most advantageous at the present moment. This method follows a locally optimal decision logic, with the expectation that such a selection will lead to a globally optimal solution[5]. This approach is a valuable tool in computing, offering fast and elegant solutions to a wide range of problems.

In addition to the greedy algorithm, there is a variation known as the iterated greedy algorithm. This method extends the greedy approach by introducing the idea of exploring multiple local solutions in the hope of finding an even more optimized global solution. It generates a sequence of solutions by iterating over greedy constructive heuristics in two main phases: destruction and construction[20]. Over the course of these iterations, the iterated greedy algorithm can accumulate knowledge about previous partial results, refining its subsequent decisions. This offers an advantage in complex problems, where the selection of a globally optimal solution may be influenced by factors not easily noticeable in a single iteration.

The algorithm's procedure begins by destroying the initial solution, with the objective of resetting all values. Subsequently, the algorithm enters an iterative cycle aimed at continuously improving the current solution. During each iteration, a controlled destruction of the current solution is performed using the percentages "j" and "d", followed by a reconstruction based on specific criteria and percentage "k". The quality of the solution is evaluated, and if a better solution is identified, it is updated as the best solution found so far. In the case of NEXOS, this procedure will end according to the response time defined by the user, who will be able to choose between one, five, and fifteen minutes, depending on how precise the selection needs to be.

4 Solution Development

The development of the NEXOS system followed core software engineering principles, encompassing requirements engineering, design, implementation, tests and project management [6]. To ensure that the system effectively met its goals, the chosen approach aligned functionalities with stakeholder needs, enabling objectives to be achieved in a structured and controlled manner. Moreover,

the project was managed using agile methodologies, with 15-day sprints and continuous task monitoring throughout the development process, which facilitated iterative improvements and better coordination[19].

In the requirements engineering phase, the functionalities and constraints of the NEXOS system were defined based on outlining key actions such as user registration and release management [17]. Non-functional requirements covered aspects like performance, security, and usability to ensure quality standards [20]. Business rules, including mandatory field validation and requirement dependencies [7], were documented in tables to support implementation. Additionally, system modeling included use case diagrams and data structures to represent entities and their relationships clearly [6], as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Use Case Diagram

The solution was developed following a structured approach using Python³ as the primary programming language, with Django⁴ for front-end implementation and Flask for back-end services. The graphical interface was built upon the commercially licensed Konrix template⁵, which provided essential pre-built components for core functionalities including release registration, visualization dashboards, and the algorithm-driven Kanban board. This implementation ensures that the mathematical model's recommendations are translated into actionable visual workflows, where color-coded tags (green for implemented, red for pending, and orange for dependent items) provide immediate status recognition, enabling efficient project tracking and decision-making.

The Kanban board serves as the visual representation of the algorithm's output, dynamically displaying requirements selected through a combination of user inputs and the mathematical model's variables. This intelligent selection process generates an optimized pathway that guides project managers in sprint and release planning. As shown in Figure 4, selected requirements appear as cards

³<https://www.python.org/>

⁴<https://www.djangoproject.com/>

⁵<https://themeforest.net/item/konrix-vue-tailwind-css-admin-dashboard-template/52400761>

in the "Sprint Backlog" column, systematically organized by client-specific sub-columns, while all registered requirements for the release remain visible in the "Product Backlog" column for comprehensive oversight.

Figure 4: NEXOS’ main output represented as a Kanban Board

Architecturally, the front-end adhered to the template’s recommended structure while incorporating custom Django applications for business logic, all deployed within a virtual environment to ensure portability[9]. The server-side implementation established a well-defined layered architecture[18], clearly separating models (domain entities), persistence (MongoDB Atlas⁶ integration via Py-Mongo), routes (REST endpoints with CORS support), and services (business logic and Firebase⁷ authentication), thereby ensuring code organization and maintainability. Figure 5 illustrates the interaction among the system’s components using a UML sequence diagram.

Figure 5: Sequence Diagram illustrating system interactions

5 Tests

The testing phase followed a stratified approach, encompassing unit, integration, system, and acceptance testing, with the objective of ensuring robustness, reliability, and compliance with the specified requirements[8] using Pytest⁸. Unit tests focused on validating isolated components, such as the MongoRepository module, ensuring the correct functioning of essential operations—data insertion, retrieval, and deletion[10]. Concurrently, integration tests

assessed the interaction between subsystems, including the handling of exceptional scenarios like invalid credentials or incomplete data requests. The code coverage analysis, performed using the Code Coverage⁹, revealed a rate of 85%, indicating a substantial validation of the codebase[11]. Critical components, such as services and routes, were prioritized, while lower-complexity modules received coverage proportional to their functional impact.

System testing was conducted in collaboration with the FalaJogador project, developed by Myllena Moreira Miranda, a member of the Meninas Digitais Valerinas group at the State University of Santa Catarina (UDESC), Ibirama campus. This partnership enabled the evaluation of the system’s behavior under varying requirements and priorities[16], leading to adjustments in the processing algorithm and database integration.

Subsequently, acceptance testing was carried out in two distinct stages, involving participants and software engineering professionals from UDESC/Ibirama. These tests aimed to simulate a diverse range of scenarios[21], including those not initially foreseen during development. This iterative approach facilitated continuous refinement, aligning the system with both business rules and end-user expectations[13].

6 Results and Discussions

To conduct the user evaluations, a testing document was prepared with detailed instructions about the scenarios to be tested¹⁰. Participants were allowed to select projects and a number of requirements for analysis that didn’t exceed twenty due to database space. Groups were formed based on the participant’s level of experience with requirement selection, aiming to assess whether the performance of the NEXOS system varied according to experience. The main goal was to verify the effectiveness of NEXOS as a support tool for release and sprint planning. Participants compared the requirements selected by the algorithm with those they would have chosen using the traditional method, allowing for a direct comparison between the two approaches involving a software development laboratory of UDESC Alto Vale¹¹ and software engineering professionals.

6.1 Project 1 – Voting System

Sample description: Two participants with low experience in requirement selection evaluated nine requirements, 88% of which had interdependencies. **System/scenario description:** High structural complexity due to the large number of interdependent requirements. **Results:** The algorithm selected relevant requirements but failed to fully comply with mathematical constraints. Specifically, it selected dependent requirements without including the interconnected elements (See Figure 6). **Discussion:** Additional tests were conducted by increasing the algorithm’s runtime and reducing the number of dependencies. The findings indicate that in projects where over 80% of the requirements are interdependent, the algorithm struggles to make optimal selections, likely due to the combinatorial complexity introduced by the dependencies.

⁶<https://www.mongodb.com/>

⁷<https://firebase.google.com/>

⁸<https://docs.pytest.org/en/stable/>

⁹<https://coverage.readthedocs.io/en/7.8.0/>

¹⁰<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15383940>

¹¹<https://www.udesc.br/ceavi/empds>

Figure 6: Kanban Board - Project 1

Figure 8: Kanban Board - Project 3

6.2 Project 2 – Internal Games

Sample description: Two participants with low experience in requirement selection evaluated eight requirements that only had three dependencies. **System/scenario description:** Low structural complexity with mostly independent requirements. **Results:** The algorithm selected the same requirements as those chosen by the participants for project initiation (See Figure 7). **Discussion:** The low number of dependencies favored the algorithm’s performance, which successfully aligned with human decision-making in prioritization.

Figure 7: Kanban Board - Project 2

6.3 Project 3 – RoupAi

Sample description: One participant with high experience in requirement selection evaluated eleven requirements, the project had two clients and only three requirements were dependent. **System/scenario description:** Multiple stakeholders with minimal requirement dependencies. **Results:** The algorithm selected the same initial requirements as the participants (See Figure 8). **Discussion:** The distribution of requirements across clients did not affect the algorithm’s performance, demonstrating its adaptability to multi-stakeholder contexts.

6.4 Project 4 – AYL

Sample description: One participant with low experience in requirement selection evaluated eleven requirements and more than half of them had dependencies. **System/scenario description:** Intermediate complexity with a significant number of dependencies. **Results:** The algorithm selected good initial requirements but failed to fully respect the mathematical constraints, choosing a dependent requirement without its corresponding counterpart (See Figure 9). **Discussion:** This behavior supports the earlier findings, suggesting that performance declines when dependency density is elevated.

Figure 9: Kanban Board - Project 4

6.5 Project 5 – Pet Digital

Sample description: One participant with low experience in requirement selection evaluated ten requirements, and more than half were interdependent. **System/scenario description:** Moderate complexity with heterogeneous dependency distribution. **Results:** The algorithm selected the same initial requirements as the participants (See Figure 10). **Discussion:** Despite the dependencies, the algorithm performed well, indicating that problems tend to arise only when dependency density becomes too high.

Figure 10: Kanban Board - Project 5

6.6 Consolidated Discussions

Although limitations were observed in scenarios with a high level of inter-dependencies, the NEXOS algorithm generally performed well. It is important to note that the system is designed to assist, not replace, human decision-making. Users retain the ability to adjust the proposed scope, especially in complex cases where inter dependencies strongly affect feasibility.

Evaluation form responses indicated that in approximately 80% of the cases, the system significantly aided in planning. The distribution of participants by experience level had no substantial impact on results, as both more and less experienced users reported selecting requirements similar to those recommended by the algorithm.

Figure 11: Algorithm effectiveness in planning support

Figure 12: Selection accuracy by user experience

The graphs presented below were generated using the Matplotlib¹² library in Python. The data used for these visualizations were directly imported from the evaluation form¹³ responses, ensuring an accurate representation of the participants' feedback.

Responses related to scope modifications were generally positive, with concerns mainly arising in cases involving high dependency levels. The second part of the evaluation, based on the System Usability Scale (SUS)[3], also yielded positive results, with an average score of 9.25, reflecting high perceived usability[2].

Figure 13: SUS rate result

As for threats to the study's validity, the limited number of evaluators is noted as a potential issue. To address this, future evaluations with a larger number of projects and participants are recommended to enhance result representativeness.

7 Concluding Remarks

The development and evaluation of the NEXOS system demonstrated its potential to support decision-making processes during release and sprint planning by automating the selection of software requirements based on dependency constraints and project context. Through structured tests involving users with varying levels of experience, the system proved to be a valuable tool in approximately 80% of the cases analyzed. Even in scenarios involving high interdependency among requirements—where the algorithm's performance faced certain limitations—the results remained consistent with user expectations, reinforcing the tool's practical relevance.

For future work, it is intended to expand the algorithm's capabilities by incorporating additional constraints and parameters, such as the number of available developers, estimated effort per requirement (card), and total time allocated for a given sprint or release. These enhancements aim to bring the recommendation engine closer to real-world conditions faced by agile teams. Furthermore, deploying the platform on a public server is also envisioned, enabling broader accessibility and allowing professionals to integrate NEXOS into their daily project planning routines.

8 Artifacts

All artifacts developed throughout this study are publicly available in: <https://github.com/luizanurnberg/tcc-nexos-server.git>, <https://github.com/luizanurnberg/tcc-nexos-web.git>, <https://github.com/luizanurnberg/tcc-nexos-statistic.git>.

¹²<https://matplotlib.org/>

¹³https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdr_7uREVM2cdAixgYdjyiXgPJ34zQZ_vE8N3zev9F4lmOSTA/viewform?usp=sharing

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